

Simulation of tau decays, ambiguities and anomalous couplings

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December 21, 2025

IFJPAN-IV-2025-25

Abstract

From the perspective of low energy τ decays and radiative corrections in decays, not much has changed since the last, **Tau23** conference. Also, **TAUOLA**, τ decay library, and **PHOTOS** for radiative corrections in decays have not changed much, neither for QED nor for New Physics processes application. Progress was in domain of flexibilities for applications and in the domain of *New Physicists*. There was progress with use of exclusive exponentiation (**KKMC Monte Carlo**) to evaluate quality of τ pair formation and decay factorization, with Collins-Soper and **Mustraal** frames. Ambiguities for New Physics or other processes could be thus addressed. Associated projects of **KKMC f77** and **KKMCee C++**, are presented: (i) $\pi^+\pi^-$ pair production at **Belle II** energies, interesting input for $\Pi_{\gamma\gamma}(s)$, (ii) attribution of helicity like labels for τ 's in simulated **HepMC3** format events, (iii) also τ polarimetric vectors prepared for user application of New Physics.

1 Introduction

The **KKMC** [1,2] program for simulation of lepton-pair productions in e^+e^- collisions, **TAUOLA** [3,4] for τ lepton decays and **PHOTOS** [5,6] for radiative corrections in decays are long term projects consisting of construction of Monte Carlo generators, but requiring massive theoretical effort as well. Projects efforts were extending over more than 40 years of time. Many people were involved in the developments, and the programs have been presented in many occasions, in particular at all τ -lepton conferences since the beginning of the conference cycle. Now, the necessary and delicate phase of contributing authors generation change, require the transfer of various skills and expertise. This is major challenge of the forthcoming several years, but it is difficult to address. The presentation of the programs themselves is of limited interest this year, as not much changes were introduced. Instead, presentation of associated activities may be of interest. That will be covered in the following section, each presenting different, but correlated with the listed Monte Carlo programs projects.

2 On feasibility of using **KKMC Monte Carlo** for $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\gamma$.

An old application for use of **KKMC** for π -pair production got lost. Only some plots prepared by S. Jadach survived, see [7] and [8]. However interest in the application remains. I was asked if something can be done to recover. I found it easier to prepare implementation in a new but in distinct manner, more suitable for **Belle II** quick implementation. That means re-weighting

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Figure 1: (a) Ratio of: reweighted $\pi^+\pi^-$ invariant mass to generated $\mu^+\mu^-$ invariant mass. (b) The $\cos\theta$ distribution of $\mu^+\mu^-$ direction. Only hard photons events selected. **Mustraal** frame used (to be explained later). Shape of Born distribution recovered. Hard scattering angle θ is defined in the muon pair rest frame (**Mustraal** or Collins Soper). (c) The same $\cos\theta$ distribution of $\mu^+\mu^-$, but reweighted to $\pi^+\pi^-$, as previously, only hard photons events selected.

of $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-n\gamma$ (muon mass replaced with π^\pm mass into $\pi^+\pi^-$ pairs. We have followed as follows. First, only initial state bremsstrahlung was studied, for that purpose **KKMC**, and several options for QED matrix elements were used: the **CEEX0**, **CEEX1**, **CEEX2** and **CEEX2** with further improvements were compared. Suitability of the **CEEX2** choice (with or without improvements) is justified in Fig. 1 where ratio of the $\pi-\pi$ -pair invariant mass, to the one if $\mu\mu$ - pair (of π mass) is plotted. Modified matrix element was used. For the hard photon events, angular distribution of the events and events after re-weighting to π production (no bremsstrahlung) matrix elements was shown. That preliminary test, for **KKMC f77** was encouraging, but further studies with π -pair production and comparisons with other programs (as in [8]) was not completed. Project got stalled. But now, with **KKMCee C++** version offer nice project to revive [9]. This work points to another topic, that means tests and applications for spin effects in τ pair production.

3 Factorizing distributions.

The **KKMC** Monte Carlo program represents a refined project based on exclusive exponentiation and on laborious analyses and implementation of the first and second order matrix elements. However, for some tests and other applications, a simplified picture of factorizing processes into bremsstrahlung part and an effective Born. We provide only one reference on the topic [10]; the interested reader is referred to the references therein. One can find there that the studied frames found applications outside of QED and are useful for hadronic interactions as well.

Let us return to our topic. In case of the **Mustraal** frame, the θ distribution of hard bremsstrahlung events, before reweighting from muons to pions, matched well the Born $1 + \beta^2 \cos^2\theta$ shape, see Fig 1 (b). After re-weighting, Born level $\pi\pi$ shape of $\cos\theta$ distribution was recovered too. For the **Collins-Soper** frame the test worked, but with slightly lower accuracy.

Now let us address the question what the **Mustraal** frame is and why it is of interest. Originally, it was devised for ultrarelativistic muon pairs with energies around the Z peak. Now we want to use it for τ 's/ μ 's and at relatively low energies¹ What is the origin of the **Mustraal** frame? Is it only because of some lucky properties of matrix elements? At one time, the **Mustraal** frame [12] looked like a technical trick, but it originates from properties of the Lorentz group representation. That is why the applicability domain extends, even when a

¹We leave aside final-state bremsstrahlung (which can be generated with **PHOTOS** MC). Ref. [11] can be used as a starting point to study ambiguity. Initial-final-state bremsstrahlung interference remains to be checked as well. However, we can use μ -s generation of **KKMC** to estimate ambiguity.

photon is ‘replaced’ by a hadronic jet or two or more photons/jets. The solution works also in the relativistic regime, not only in the ultrarelativistic one. An important observation: ISR (or FSR) matrix element leads to a sum of two non-coherent distributions. They can be treated separately. The choice of the *Mustraal* frame exploits this property and is *useful* not only for algorithms but for the construction of observables as well.

3.1 Validating in low energy limit; *Mustraal* frame when $m_\tau/E \gg 0$

The *Mustraal* frame design was based on matrix elements calculated in the ultrarelativistic limit and for single-photon emission only. The solution worked in the ultrarelativistic limit for single and double hadronic jet emission. That was helpful to evaluate and improve *TauSpinner*, an algorithm useful in LHC applications. But what about the lower energy regime, like for τ -s at *Belle II* energies? It is an interesting exercise in itself, but also for building intuition.

KKMC has it better, so with it we can check how the factorized Born kinematics works. In the presence of the ISR, the *Mustraal* frame matches better the theoretical prediction. The plots are made with 10 million events and the statistical error is not evaluated.

$$\frac{d\sigma^{\langle Born \rangle}}{d\cos\theta} = 1 + \cos^2\theta + \left\langle \frac{m_\tau^2}{E^2} \right\rangle \sin^2\theta + \frac{3}{8} \langle A_{FB} \rangle \cos\theta \quad (1)$$

$$f_{model1} = 1 + \cos^2\theta_{CS} + F_1 \sin^2\theta_{CS} + F_2 \cos\theta_{CS} \quad (2)$$

$$f_{model2} = 1 + \cos^2\theta_M + F_1 \sin^2\theta_M + F_2 \cos\theta_M \quad (3)$$

$$E_{\tau\tau} = \frac{\text{mass of tau pair system}}{2} \quad (4)$$

We effectively sum contributions of the Born from different energies, which is why $\langle m_\tau^2/E^2 \rangle$ and $\langle A_{FB} \rangle$ are averaged. The θ_{CS} and θ_M denote the scattering angle reconstructed when Collins-Soper or *Mustraal* frames are used. How well distribution is it reproduced? We use the plots shown in Fig. 2 to evaluate. The $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes averaging over the photon spectrum generated by *KKMcee*.

(a) CM energy = 10.58 GeV

(b) CM energy = 74.06 GeV

Figure 2: Low energy validation plots: comparison of effective $\cos\theta$ distributions obtained with Collins-Soper and *Mustraal* frames with semi-analytical distributions of Born level distribution merged with *KKMcee* invariant mass generated spectrum.

The *Collins-Soper* frame is constructed for LO; no features of radiative corrections are built into the coordinate system choice. The *Mustraal* algorithm to reconstruct the event’s effective ‘Born-like’ reference frame after photon emission (NLO) uses a bit more of matrix

way of choosing the z direction, also in the case of no bremsstrahlung. Massive smearing of the z direction (adaptation to Kleiss–Stirling techniques) with respect to direct direction of boost to lab frame. To overcome this, we had to modify KKMC to store polarimetric vectors in the lab frame `tralo4(-1/-2, ...)`. In our external code, the `Mustraal` frame is used, τ momenta are projected along the z -axis. Let us provide one plot, extending validation of the `Mustraal` frame as well.

Figure 3: The figures are made at CM energy = 10.58 GeV and provide benchmark, both for our stand-alone and `KKMCee` algorithms.

Since the external reconstruction reproduces the **KKMCee helicity fractions** at the **Z pole** with sub-per-mille accuracy, it can now be confidently used to assign helicity states event-by-event, following the same strategy as adopted by the ALEPH Collaboration [13]. In particular, the validated external algorithm can serve as an independent helicity attribution tool, allowing experimental analyses to extract τ polarization and spin-correlation observables directly from generated or reconstructed data, without relying on internal `KKMC` routines. The application can attribute helicities for muons as well, if such a need arises.

Now let us focus on Polarimetric vectors and their application to new physics searches. They are stored in `HepMC3` format. With their help, we could re-do the solution presented in Ref. [14], and obtain the same results, see Fig.4. The advantage is that now we can rely on information stored in the event file only. We were not obliged to run the anomalous coupling code simultaneously with event generation. That offers flexibility for studies distinct New physics scenarios without the need to re-do each time the detector response simulation. The anomalous implementation with event weights can be repeated several times on the same production file. This saves user effort and CPU time as well.

The standalone code demonstrates consistent behaviour across both longitudinal and transverse components, yielding physically reliable results over a wide range of energy scales up to some precision. Let us note that a similar technique, but requiring phase space and not only matrix element manipulations, was used in `PHOTOS` to generate dark photons or light scalars. But this was presented at previous τ conferences.

There was still another topic covered that was of `Belle II TAUOLA` users interest. It was about so-called τ^+ and τ^- angle β distribution asymmetry in $\tau \rightarrow 3\pi\nu$ decays. The β is the angle between the lab frame momentum ($n_L^{\vec{}}$) and $\vec{q}_1 \times \vec{q}_2$, where q_1 and q_2 are the momenta of the identical hadrons in the hadronic rest frame. For identical particles, the momenta were ordered such that $|q_1| < |q_2|$. The users have noted an asymmetry in π, π, π decay mode, whereas for the K, π, π no asymmetry was observed when `CLEO` current is used. As this asymmetry is related to CP (equivalently T) symmetry breaking, it attracts attention and some results of

Figure 4: Validation result. With stand-alone tool, we have reconstructed plot of [14].

ref. [15] were recalled. Dependencies on distinct models of τ decays require attention. It may be encouraging for future measurements. At present, old ARGUS measurements [16] are available only. These decays are of particular interest because they require modelling from low and intermediate-energy QCD, but because of the limited number of hadrons, a model-independent representation of hadronic current is possible [17]. That is particularly attractive for studying interactions because non-trivial three-hadron interactions must be taken into account. The initial state is well defined by electroweak interactions. Does it hint at ambiguities in isospin rotations?

We have observed that the β angle asymmetry arises from the interference between the complex parts of the two Breit–Wigner amplitudes corresponding to the resonances. The imaginary part reflects the time evolution (or decay dynamics) of the resonant particle. The asymmetry appears when there are two secondary resonances. In the CLEO current for the K^- , π^- , π^+ mode, only one resonance is present, so no asymmetry is observed. In contrast, the TAUOLA version used in Belle II, the latest standalone code, and even the 25-year-old version of the KORALB code [18] all consistently show the asymmetry, with no differences among these versions. As we could see, the asymmetry may arise or may not arise depending on the details of the current and our physics model sophistication. This is an important data point for future improvements which seems to be sometimes taken into account and sometimes ignored. Of course all these effects would disappear in the narrow intermediate-width approximation. However, if a future, more sophisticated model makes the asymmetry disappear, then it would point (or not point) to CT violation in the hadronic sector. Of course, this depends on the comparisons with the data.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported in part by funds from the Polish National Science Centre, Poland, grant No. 2023/50/A/ST2/00224 and by the U.S. Department of Energy and Research Award No. DE-SC0022350.

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